

Innovative CNC Technology for Sustainable and Highly Efficient Manufacturing

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1 Extended Abstract

Analyses of metal-cutting processes have shown that the auxiliary components in the machine tool or its environment play a dominant role in the energy balance [1]. The power consumption of a CNC control including infeed and spindle motors usually comprises only 25 to 30% of the total input power required to operate the machine [1]. Most of the electrical energy is required to supply the auxiliary components for processing cooling lubricants, for supplying compressed air and hydraulics and for cooling of feed and spindle motors [2] [3]. A study on the energy consumption of machine tools has underlined that machines consume in standby more than 50% of the energy that is required in cutting operation [1].

In general, the efficiency of CNC power electronics is very high [2]. Based on the latest generation of power semiconductors and new control algorithm, HEIDENHAIN's generation 3 power electronics has even improved the energy balance of the control cabinet. However, a major step on the road map of carbon footprint reduction based on further efficiency improvements of the CNC electronics seems to be unrealistic. In contrast, a proper management of pumps, cooling aggregates and a reduction of the compressed air consumption promise significant energy savings [2] [3]. Consequently, HEIDENHAIN's new linear absolute position feedback systems for machine tools will no longer require compressed air during operation. A new innovative scanning technology and a new sealing concept allow proper and reliable operation without the need of compressed air.

Figure 1 shows the average input power of three different machine types which are specified in table 1, [1]. The results point out, that a high level of automation for 24/7 operation of machine tools has significant impact on the energy consumption. As parts and fixtures need to be cleaned to 100% to avoid clamping errors caused by remaining chips in the machine workspace, the energy consumption to process the cooling liquid increases significantly [1] [3]. However, automation allows significant higher throughput, and the energy consumption per part might decrease in comparison with non-automated machines.

Table 1: Machine tool concepts considered in a study on energy consumption during standby and productive operation [1].

Characteristics	Machine 1	Machine 2	Machine 3
Workpiece flow	manual	Pallet changer	Part magazine
Operation	1 shift/d	3 shift/d	3 shift/d
Redundant cutting tools	No	yes	Yes

This presentation focusses on the potential of organizational measures and manufacturing control approaches to scale down the carbon footprint of parts being produced with machine tools. Figure 1 clearly outlines the significant power consumption in standby, that is dominated by components to provide compressed air, properly tempered cooling liquid and further auxiliary components. Switching off the auxiliary components in standby

would significantly improve the energy balance but lead to a transient state in the thermal equilibrium of the machine and to corresponding accuracy problems of the machine tool.

To optimize the carbon footprint of machine tools under operation and parts to be produced with them, manufacturing control needs to assure that:

1. standby operation and nonproductive time in general is minimized or – if possible - completely avoided,
2. the metal removal rate is maximized regarding the thermal load capacity of cutting tools and the mechanical load capacity of tools, fixtures and machine.

Three different manufacturing control principles provided by modern CNC technology and digitalization concepts are considered in this presentation (figure 2 and 3):

1. Feedforward control based perfectly validated NC programs.
2. Feedback process control based on local process intelligence provided by the CNC.
3. Feedback process control involving the manufacturing team.

The feedforward control approach covers the idea of controlling all machine operations required for a steady and error free part production by a perfectly defined process input (figure 3, left). In manufacturing, the NC code as the relevant input to control the machine operation needs to be validated to 100% with respect to programming errors, that generate collisions and tool overload and – as a consequence - unexpected downtime. HEIDENHAIN's latest control generation TNC7 offers outstanding simulation performance to monitor collisions between machine components, fixtures and tools. Combined with the software option Dynamic Collision Monitoring in the second generation, the risk of unexpected downtime and useless energy consumption in standby due to collisions can be reduced close to zero. The manufacturing job can be validated on the NC code level with a programming station enhanced to a digital twin of the real machine (figure 4).

A new cutting data calculator provided by HEIDENHAIN's TNC offers outstanding performance to operate the cutting tools at their thermal and mechanical load limit in a highly process reliable mode. Based on a TNC-integrated digitalization of material data and HEIDENHAIN's next level of trochoidal milling offered with Optimized Contour Milling (OCM), the energy consumption per part can be reduced up to 67% (figure 5 and 6). The load control on the cutting tools avoids nonproductive time and waste parts caused by tool breakage. As a result, HEIDENHAIN's approach to operate the cutting tools at their thermal and mechanical load limit offers significant potential to reduce the carbon footprint per part in the sense of feedforward process control.

With the feedforward process control approach errors cannot be totally avoided. As an example, raw material characteristics might vary locally and tools or the machine might be damaged (figure 7). Consequently, the machine will produce waste parts or will stop unexpectedly. To reduce the carbon footprint, process errors need to be identified and feed back to the process control algorithm of the CNC (figure 3, middle). HEIDENHAIN's numerical controls provide local process intelligence to monitor machine and tool overload and offer a bundle of powerful measures to automatically keep the machine in productive mode in case of process errors. The new software option Process Monitoring significantly reduce the reaction time in case of tool breakage. Process Monitoring identifies process irregularities and stops the manufacturing job immediately. Figure 8 shows the impact of an unexpected nonproductive time due to tool breakage. The reaction time of the shop floor staff will lead to useless energy consumption of the machine, whereas the software option Process Monitoring manages to recognize the error and to get the machine into productive operation with very short reaction time. By that, impacts of tool breakage on the carbon footprint per part can be controlled down to a minimum.

If the machining process needs to be aborted because of process errors, the machine might be back in productive operation after the next workpiece is in the machine. Nevertheless, process errors need to be analyzed by the shop floor team to finish the corresponding manufacturing job successfully. Digitalization can provide detailed diagnosis information on process errors, like the corresponding NC line and spindle load in case of a tool breakage or warning and error messages of the CNC control. Monitoring services like the HEIDENHAIN StateMonitor will inform the shop floor team via messenger services on process irregularities. A detailed bundle of relevant information is attached to the process irregularity. The shop floor team can close the loop efficiently and restart the manufacturing job with a well mapped-out set of corrected process parameters (figure 3, right). In this way, digitalization significantly contributes to a fast and reactive manufacturing control loop closed efficiently by the shop floor team.

2 References

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Figure 1: Average input power of three different machine tool concepts during standby and cutting operation [1].

Figure 2: Manufacturing job processing and digitalization

Figure 3: Feedforward and feedback-based process control

Figure 4: Advanced precheck of the manufacturing job with NC code based 3D simulation including tooling and fixtures of machining setup

Figure 5: Comparison of conventional milling and Optimized Contour Milling - the next generation of trochoidal milling. Tool lifetime can be exceeded 3 times and machining time is reduced by factor 3.

Figure 6: Productivity improvement and reduced energy consumption by optimized cutting parameter and tool path based on the cutting tests shown in figure 5.

Figure 7: Enhance productivity by automation and local process intelligence on the CNC level to avoid machine down time caused by component overload and process errors.

Figure 8: Case study on the impact of tool breakage in automated manufacturing on productivity and energy consumption with and without process monitoring. Machine 2 refers to the characteristics in Table 1 and Figure 1.